
Common Accidents in Paediatric Practice; Current Evidence for a 4-Pronged Strategic Framework for Prevention

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ABSTRACT

Accidents are untoward events that occur inadvertently and lead to injuries or diseases. In healthcare settings, both patients and healthcare workers are at risk of being victims. By virtue of children's evolving developmental maturity, caring for them puts all parties more at risk. Having a comprehensive framework to prevent accidents in paediatric practice is therefore crucial.

This paper aims to utilize the principles of primordial, primary, secondary and tertiary preventive strategies to design a framework for preventing accidents in paediatric healthcare settings, in the light of current evidence. Common cases selected to exemplify the framework include needle stick injury, exposure to blood-borne infections, post-injection traumatic neuropathy, post-injection abscess, Nicolau syndrome, fluid overload, and drug overdose.

Vital to preventing the selected injuries and disorders is a multidisciplinary team of relevant experts, including paediatricians, paediatric surgeons, orthopaedic surgeons, burns and plastic surgeons, neurosurgeons, toxicologists, pharmacists, microbiologists, infectious disease physicians, anaesthetists, and public health physicians.

KEYWORDS: Accidents, Paediatric practice, 4-pronged preventive strategy, Multidisciplinary team

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
15 August 2022

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

INTRODUCTION

Accidents have been defined as unexpected and unintentional events that lead to injury.¹ In healthcare settings, accidents do not only result in physical injuries; they could potentially have biological and psychological impacts on patients, caregivers, healthcare providers and support staff. Children, by virtue of their evolving physical and cognitive maturity, pose more risk of accidents in hospitals and clinics. It is therefore crucial for paediatric healthcare workers and managers to always anticipate and avoid such incidents.

This paper elucidates a critical strategic framework for preventing accidents in paediatric practice. Common cases were selected to exemplify the framework; they include needle stick injury (NSI), exposure to blood-borne infections, post-injection traumatic neuropathy, post-injection abscess,

Nicolau syndrome, fluid overload, and drug overdose. The strategies are presented within the context of a 4-pronged interventional model, namely the primordial and Leavell's primary, secondary and tertiary levels of prevention.^{2,3}

THE FOUR LEVELS OF PREVENTION

Primordial strategy is a health promotive population-based measure that prevents the emergence of risk factors for injuries and diseases.^{4,5} Primary strategy is a specific measure that targets susceptible populations; it reduces the incidence of a specified injury or disease by addressing the risk factors for or increasing resistance to the morbidity.^{2,5,6} Secondary strategy targets the latent ("hidden") stage of a disease or injury; it limits progression to the symptomatic stage through early detection and prompt intervention, thus reducing the

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prevalence.^{2,4} Tertiary strategy targets the symptomatic stage; it limits disability at the early phase of the injury or disease, and rehabilitates the victim at the late phase.^{2,4,6}

Prevention of needle stick injury and exposure to blood-borne infections

Primordial strategy: (a) Training of clinical and support staff on NSI and standard precautions; (b) Training of clinical staff on phlebotomy techniques in children; (c) Designating trained phlebotomists to obtain blood samples and secure intravenous (IV) access in children.

Primary strategy: (a) Observing standard precautions when performing procedures in children; (b) Placing sharps containers at multiple locations in the wards and clinics; (c) Pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) with hepatitis B vaccine (HBV_{vac}) given to all healthcare workers and support staff.

Secondary strategy: (a) Washing wound/breeched skin thoroughly (without squeezing) with water and soap.⁷ Alcohol, a virucidal agent to human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV), can also be applied. Other virucidal agents include chlorhexidine, iodophors and chloroxylonol; (b) Irrigating mucous membrane with large amount of water (eyes with saline or water); (c) Incident reporting;

HIV post-exposure intervention^{8,9}

(d) Unless known to have HIV, the source is tested for HIV with a fourth-generation combined antigen-antibody test; (e) The victim is tested for HIV infection; (f) If the benefit of antiretroviral (ARV) therapy outweighs the risk of infection and potential drug toxicities, post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is offered to the victim within 1-2 hours while awaiting results (*ARV PEP Regimen: Children <10 years old – Zidovudine + Lamivudine + Lopinavir-ritonavir, Adolescents and adults – Tenofovir + Lamivudine/Emtricitabine + Lopinavir-ritonavir/Atazanavir-ritonavir*); (g) PEP is discontinued after four weeks or when the source is confirmed to be HIV negative and there is no suspicion of acute HIV infection;

*HBV post-exposure intervention*¹⁰

(h) The source is tested for hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) unless the source is known to have HBV infection, or the victim had completed the standard HBV_{vac} series (*given at 0, 1 and 6 months*) and is a vaccine responder [*antibody to HBsAg (anti-HBs) titre is ≥ 10 mIU/mL after complete series*] prior to exposure; (i) The victim is tested for HBsAg and anti-HBs (*anti-HBs is tested only if fully vaccinated*); (j) PEP, comprising hepatitis B immunoglobulin (HBIG) and HBV_{vac}, is offered to the victim if the source is positive for HBsAg and the victim is a vaccine non-responder or is unvaccinated/incompletely vaccinated. If eligible for PEP, HBIG is given within 24 hours or not later than seven days, HBV_{vac} is administered simultaneously at a different site, a second dose of HBIG is given one month after, and HBV_{vac} series are completed; (k) Follow-up testing for HBsAg and antibody to hepatitis B core antigen (anti-HBc) is done six months after exposure. A health worker can provide care to

patients within this period, but cannot donate body fluids, tissues or organs;

*HCV post-exposure intervention*¹¹

(l) The source is tested for HCV ribonucleic acid (RNA), or antibody to HCV (anti-HCV) if HCV RNA is not available; (m) The victim is tested for anti-HCV within 48 hours provided the source is positive for HCV RNA/anti-HCV; (n) If the victim's anti-HCV is positive, HCV RNA is assayed – if negative, it is repeated at least three weeks following exposure. Positive HCV RNA within 48 hours indicates pre-existing HCV infection and requires immediate referral for comprehensive care. The origin of infection is indeterminable after at least three weeks if HCV RNA becomes positive; (o) If the victim's initial anti-HCV is negative, HCV RNA is assayed at least three weeks following exposure, or anti-HCV is repeated at least six weeks after. Positive HCV RNA at three or six weeks indicates source-induced HCV infection, while a negative result does not require further testing; (p) Early diagnosis of source-induced HCV infection and prompt initiation of treatment are crucial, as current evidence does not support PEP for HCV infection.

Tertiary prevention: *NSI is often associated with pain and emotional stress caused by exposure to potentially serious infections, hence, (a) Pain should be controlled with analgesics; (b) Post-exposure testing should be expedited; (c) PEP counselling should be as explicit as possible; (d) Victim should be referred early for preemptive psychotherapy; (e) Victims with symptomatic source-induced HIV, HBV or HCV infection should be referred early for comprehensive care.*

Prevention of post-injection traumatic neuropathy, post-injection abscess and Nicolau syndrome

Primordial strategy: (a) Formulating restrictive policies on indications for injections in children; (b) Creating public awareness to correct the misconception about the “magic” effect of injections; (c) Enforcing national and local laws prohibiting quackery (d) Employing qualified clinical staff into children's hospitals, clinics and wards.

Primary strategy: (a) Using the right injection sites [*Intramuscular (IM) injections: children up to two years – vastus lateralis of anterolateral thigh, children 3 to 10 years – deltoid muscle/vastus lateralis of anterolateral thigh, 11 to 18 years old – deltoid muscle, Subcutaneous (SC) injections: ≤ 1 year old – thigh area, ≥ 1 year old – upper outer triceps area, Intradermal (ID) injections: < 2 months old – deltoid area, ≥ 2 months old – proximal ventral forearm/proximal dorsal forearm/deltoid area*]¹²⁻¹⁴ (b) Using the right needle gauge (*IM: 22-25, SC: 23-25, ID: 25-26*), right needle length (*IM: 16-32 mm, SC: 16 mm, ID: 12.7 mm*), right angulation (*IM: 90°, SC: 45°*), right technique (*IM: Z-track*), right injection depth (*ID: 0.7 mm*) and right patient positioning¹²⁻¹⁶; (c) Avoiding the gluteal region in children < 5 years old^{16,17}; (d) If the gluteus must be used in children ≥ 5 years old, the ventrogluteal (*gluteal triangle*) rather than dorsogluteal region (*upper outer quadrant*) is preferred

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^{16,18,19}; **(e)** Using a special device to deliver ID injections to enhance precision ¹⁴; **(f)** Adopting percutaneous route for BCG vaccination ²⁰; **(g)** Minimizing glass particle contamination of injections by partially wrapping the ampoule neck, breaking the ampoule from an outward direction, and using filter needle for injection ²¹; **(h)** Minimizing the risk of post-injection abscess (PIA) by maintaining a sterile field of injection and adequately diluting drug solutions. Hypertonic drug solutions have been shown to be an important risk factor for PIA ²²; **(i)** Minimizing the risk of Nicolau syndrome by allowing crystals in refrigerated drug to dissolve before injecting, and avoiding periarterial injection ^{23,24}; **(j)** Properly restraining an uncooperative child during injection administration; **(k)** Training and retraining of staff on standard sequential technique and recommended anatomical sites for injections in children.^{25,26}

Secondary strategy:

Traumatic injection neuropathy (TIN)

(a) Recognizing the early symptoms and signs (*pain, paraesthesia, causalgia*); **(b)** Incident reporting; **(c)** Evaluating with magnetic resonance neurography, electromyography, nerve conduction studies; **(d)** Immediate flooding of subgluteal space with physiologic fluid following emergence of early symptoms and signs ¹⁶; **(e)** Controlling pain with acetaminophen, gabapentin or tricyclic antidepressant following emergence of early symptoms and signs ²⁷

Nicolau syndrome (embolia medicamentosa or livedoid dermatitis)

*Presents with intense pain immediately after injection, followed by erythema and violaceous patch within minutes to hours. Later turns haemorrhagic, forms deep ulcer and heals with atrophic scar in weeks to months.*²³ **(f)** Recognizing the early symptoms and signs; **(g)** Incident reporting; **(h)** Evaluating the extent of injury with ultrasonography, magnetic resonance imaging; **(i)** Use of cold compress is discouraged (*it may be of no benefit and may worsen complication*) ^{28,29}; **(j)** Controlling pain with analgesics.

Tertiary strategy:

Traumatic injection neuropathy

(a) Early recognition of paralytic TIN; **(b)** Early referral of paralytic TIN for physiotherapy ³⁰; **(c)** Surgery – surgical exploration within 3 to 6 months of injury, surgical nerve repair, dynamic elastic splint, musculotendinous transposition/femoral lengthening¹⁶; **(d)** Trans-sacral methylprednisolone block for sciatic TIN ³¹; **(e)** Follow-up check for nerve regeneration

Post-injection abscess

(f) Controlling pain with acetaminophen or ibuprofen; **(g)** Drainage of BCG-induced suppurative lymphadenitis [*BCG injection site (deltoid) reaction and abscess do not require treatment in immunocompetent individuals*] ³²; **(h)** Treatment of extra-deltoid BCG-induced tubercular cold abscess using anti-tubercular drugs, clarithromycin and antigavity

drainage ^{33–35}; **(i)** Prompt drainage of infectious PIA and commencement of appropriate antimicrobial therapy;

Nicolau syndrome ^{23,24,36,37}

(j) Controlling pain with acetaminophen or ibuprofen; **(k)** Bed rest; **(l)** Debridement; **(m)** Dressing; **(n)** Vasoactive agent – alprostadil, pentoxifylline; **(o)** Anticoagulant – subcutaneous heparin; **(p)** Hyperbaric oxygen; **(q)** Topical steroid; **(r)** Surgery (*rarely indicated*)

Prevention of fluid overload

Primordial strategy: **(a)** Formulating restrictive policies on the indications for intravenous fluid (IVF) in children; **(b)** Creating public awareness to correct the misconception about the “magic” effect of IVF; **(c)** Enforcing national and local laws prohibiting quackery; **(d)** Employing qualified staff into children’s wards, clinics, dialysis units and dispensaries; **(e)** Procuring quality-assured paediatric fluid delivery sets and machines.

Primary strategy: **(a)** Formulating evidence-based protocol for fluid therapy and renal replacement therapy on a ‘case by case’ basis; **(b)** Adapting fluid regimen based on availability of facility for haemodynamic monitoring ³⁸; **(c)** Selecting the type of maintenance fluid on the basis of serum sodium level and the risk of developing syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone ³⁹; **(d)** Appropriate calculation of maintenance fluid requirement (*using Holliday-Segar formula*) **(e)** Using the minimum volume of fluid for drug administration ⁴⁰; **(f)** Using infusion pump to deliver IVF, parenteral nutrition, blood products and drug infusions; **(g)** Close haemodynamic monitoring during administration of IVF and blood; **(h)** Regular monitoring of delivery system during fluid administration ⁴¹; **(i)** Regular fluid balance check during fluid administration; **(j)** Training and retraining of staff on calculation of fluid rate.

Secondary strategy: **(a)** Regular calculation of %fluid overload
$$\left(\frac{\text{Daily fluid intake (L)} - \text{Total fluid output (L)}}{\text{Baseline body weight (kg)}} \times 100 \right)$$

during fluid administration. The patient remains asymptomatic until %fluid overload approaches 10%.^{42–44}; **(b)** In critically ill and kidney-impaired patients, screening with lung ultrasound (*lung ultrasound is more sensitive at the asymptomatic phase than auscultation and chest radiograph*), echocardiography, bioimpedance spectroscopy, natriuretic peptides, inferior vena cava collapsibility index, relative blood volume monitoring ^{42,43,45}; **(c)** Stopping fluid therapy or reducing fluid rate **(d)** In critically ill patients, administering low dose diuretic, e.g., 0.2 mg/kg of IV furosemide. ⁴⁰

Tertiary strategy: **(a)** Recognizing clinical features of fluid overload (*new-onset oedema, new tachypnoea/dyspnoea, new tachycardia, jugular venous distension, pulmonary rales, hypoxia, increasing liver size, rapid weight gain*) ^{40,42}; **(b)** Administering therapeutic doses of diuretics, e.g., furosemide, torsemide, bumetanide, thiazide diuretic, spironolactone, aminophylline, theophylline (*single prophylactic dose of theophylline is recommended in severe*

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perinatal asphyxia – a risk factor for acute kidney injury and fluid overload)^{40,42}; (c) Extracorporeal therapies, e.g., renal replacement therapy⁴²; (d) Avoidance of sodium-containing drugs in kidney-impaired patients⁴³; (e) Early switch to enteral fluid and nutrition; (f) Early ambulation.

Prevention of drug overdose

Primordial strategy: (a) Enforcing national and local laws prohibiting quackery; (b) Employing qualified staff into children's wards, clinics and dispensaries.

Primary strategy: (a) Formulating evidence-based protocol for drug therapy; (b) Providing drug formulary in wards, clinics and dispensaries, and its regular use by healthcare workers; (c) Training and retraining of clinical staff on calculation of oral and parenteral drug volume; (d) Keeping all oral and parenteral drugs away from the patient's bedside; (e) Only clinical staff should administer oral and parenteral drugs.

Secondary strategy: (a) Stopping administration of the offending drug; (b) Laboratory investigations, as appropriate, e.g., toxicologic screen of blood and urine, arterial blood gases, liver function test, renal function test; (c) Activated charcoal, if: the offending drug is adsorbable, the risk of toxicity is significant, the time since drug ingestion is < 1 hour, there is no contraindication to use, the benefits outweigh the risks⁴⁶; (d) Stomach pumping or gastric lavage (*current evidence show safety concerns and minimal benefits*)⁴⁶; (e) Induced emesis (*No longer recommended*)⁴⁶; (f) Whole bowel irrigation – done with osmotically-balanced polyethylene glycol to reduce the gastro-intestinal transit time. Useful in overdose of sustained-release drugs (e.g., iron preparations)⁴⁶; (g) Urinary alkalization using isotonic IVF bolus (*cautiously administered*) and IV sodium bicarbonate, provided the offending drug is: a weak acid with pKa 3.0 to 7.5, minimally bound to protein, primarily distributed in the extracellular space, eliminated by the kidneys largely unchanged⁴⁷; (h) Forced diuresis (*not recommended*)⁴⁸; (i) IV lipid emulsion – promotes sequestration of drug in the lipid phase. Useful in overdose of local anaesthetic agents, calcium channel and beta blockers⁴⁶; (j) Antidote, if existent and indicated; (k) Establishment of a poison control unit.⁴⁹

Tertiary strategy: (a) Early recognition of classic toxidrome (*sympathomimetic, anticholinergic, cholinergic, sedative, hypnotic, hallucinogenic symptoms and signs*)⁴⁶; (b) Early recognition of signs and symptoms of specific drug toxicity; (c) Antidote, if existent; (d) IV lipid emulsion – useful in cardiovascular collapse following overdose of local anaesthetic agent⁴⁶; (e) Urinary alkalization, if applicable; (f) Haemodialysis, if applicable; (g) Haemoperfusion, if applicable; (h) Albumin dialysis, if applicable⁵⁰; (i) Haemofiltration, if applicable and where haemodialysis is not available; (j) Exchange blood transfusion, if applicable and where haemodialysis is not available; (k) Therapeutic plasma exchange, if applicable^{50,51}; (l) Cerebrospinal fluid exchange – useful in overdose of intrathecal methotrexate⁵⁰; (m)

Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation and emergency cardiopulmonary bypass, if indicated.⁵⁰

CONCLUSION

Accidents in paediatric healthcare settings should always be anticipated, and efforts should be made at preventing them. The 4-pronged strategic framework presented above can be a useful tool to minimize risks to patients, caregivers, healthcare workers, and support staff.

A multidisciplinary approach is key to preventing accidents relating to needle sticks, blood-borne infections, injections, fluids, and drugs in paediatric practice.

Funding

This article was not funded by any individual or organization.

Competing Interests

There are no conflicts of interests

REFERENCES

- I. Bonilla-Escobar FJ, Gutiérrez MI. Injuries are not accidents: Towards a culture of prevention. *Colombia Medica*. 2014;45(3):132–5.
- II. Katz D, Elmore J, Wild D, Lucan S. *Jekel's Epidemiology, Biostatistics, Preventive Medicine, and Public Health*. 4th ed. Philadelphia: Saunders, Elsevier; 2014. 173–180 p.
- III. Caplan G. *Principles of preventive psychiatry*. Basic books; 1964.
- IV. Nte A, Yaguo-Ide L. Preventive Paediatrics. In: Azubuike JC, Nkanginieme KEO, Ezechukwu C, Nte AR, Adedoyin OT, editors. *Paediatrics and Child Health in a Tropical Region*. 3rd ed. Lagos: Educational Printing and Publishing; 2016. p. 73–92.
- V. Gillman MW. Primordial prevention of cardiovascular disease. *Circulation*. 2015;131(7):599–601.
- VI. Offord DR. Selection of levels of prevention. *Addictive behaviors*. 2000;25(6):833–42.
- VII. Boyce JM, Pittet D. Guideline for hand hygiene in health-care settings: recommendations of the Healthcare Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee and the HICPAC/SHEA/APIC/IDSA Hand Hygiene Task Force [Internet]. Vol. 23, *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology*. Cambridge University Press; 2002 [cited 2022 Aug 7]. Available from: file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/cdc_6674_DS1.pdf
- VIII. Panlilio AL, Cardo DM, Grohskopf LA, Heneine W, Ross CS. Updated US Public Health Service guidelines for the management of occupational exposures to HIV and recommendations for postexposure prophylaxis [Internet]. Vol. 54, *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*:

Common Accidents in Paediatric Practice; Current Evidence for a 4-Pronged Strategic Framework for Prevention

- Recommendations and Reports. JSTOR; 2005 [cited 2022 Aug 7]. Available from: file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/cdc_6646_DS1.pdf
- IX. WHO. Guidelines on post-exposure prophylaxis for HIV and the use of co-trimoxazole prophylaxis for HIV-related infections among adults, adolescents and children: recommendations for a public health approach. World Health Organization; 2014.
- X. Schillie SF, Murphy T v, Sawyer M, Ly K, Hughes E, Jiles R, et al. CDC guidance for evaluating health-care personnel for hepatitis B virus protection and for administering postexposure management [Internet]. 2013 Dec [cited 2022 Aug 7]. Available from: file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/cdc_26308_DS1.pdf
- XI. Moorman AC, de Perio MA, Goldschmidt R, Chu C, Kuhar D, Henderson DK, et al. Testing and Clinical Management of Health Care Personnel Potentially Exposed to Hepatitis C Virus — CDC Guidance, United States, 2020 [Internet]. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report: Recommendations and Reports. 2020 Jul [cited 2022 Aug 1]. Available from: https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/69/rr/rr6906a1.htm?s_cid=rr6906a1_w
- XII. Barron C, Cocoman A. Administering intramuscular injections to children: what does the evidence say? *Journal of Children's and Young People's Nursing*. 2008;2(3):138–44.
- XIII. CDC. Vaccine Administration: Needle Gauge and Length [Internet]. Vaccine Recommendations and Guidelines of the ACIP. 2022 [cited 2022 Aug 1]. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/vaccines/hcp/acip-recs/general-recs/administration.html>
- XIV. van Mulder TJS, van Nuffel D, Demolder M, de Meyer G, Moens S, Beyers KCL, et al. Skin thickness measurements for optimal intradermal injections in children. *Vaccine*. 2020;38(4):763–8.
- XV. Hiraishi Y, Nandakumar S, Choi SO, Lee JW, Kim YC, Posey JE, et al. Bacillus Calmette-Guerin vaccination using a microneedle patch. *Vaccine*. 2011;29(14):2626–36.
- XVI. Jung Kim H, Hyun Park S. Sciatic nerve injection injury. *J Int Med Res*. 2014;42(4):887–97.
- XVII. Alonge IAO, Akinwola MO. Post-injection sciatic neuropathy: a five-year review of cases managed in a paediatric hospital in Ibadan, Nigeria. *AJPARS*. 2010;2(1):10–3.
- XVIII. Arslan GG, Özden D. Creating a change in the use of ventrogluteal site for intramuscular injection. *Patient Prefer Adherence*. 2018;12:1749.
- XIX. Mishra P, Stringer MD. Sciatic nerve injury from intramuscular injection: a persistent and global problem. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2010;64(11):1573–9.
- XX. Hawkridge A, Hatherill M, Little F, Goetz MA, Barker L, Mahomed H, et al. Efficacy of percutaneous versus intradermal BCG in the prevention of tuberculosis in South African infants: randomised trial. *BMJ*. 2008;337:a2052.
- XXI. Chiannikulchai N, Kejkornkaew S. Safety concerns with glass particle contamination: improving the standard guidelines for preparing medication injections. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*. 2021;33(2):1–6.
- XXII. Urakova N, Urakov A. Osmotic Activity of Drugs is an Important Factor of Their Local Action at the Injection Site: What We Don't Use to Prevent Post-Injection Abscesses. *JPRI*. 2021;33(59b):647–50.
- XXIII. James WD, Elston DM, Treat JR, Rosenbach MA, Neuhaus IM. Contact Dermatitis and Drug Eruptions . 13th ed. Elsevier; 2020. 92–139 p.
- XXIV. Senel E. Nicolau syndrome as an avoidable complication. *J Family Community Med*. 2012;19(1):52–3.
- XXV. Gutierrez JJP, Munakomi S. Intramuscular Injection. *StatPearls* [Internet]. StatPearls Publishing; 2022.
- XXVI. Kim HJ, Park SK, Park SH. Upper limb nerve injuries caused by intramuscular injection or routine venipuncture. *Anesth Pain Med*. 2017;12(2):103–10.
- XXVII. Keskinbora K, Aydinli I. Treatment of neuropathic pain due to sciatic nerve injury following intramuscular injection with gabapentine in a child. *Pediatric Anesthesia*. 2008;18(11):1134–5.
- XXVIII. Jam TE, Nejad RM, Farooqi MSD, Rahimi R, Mousavi SM. Nicolau syndrome following the injection of Pentavalent vaccine: A case report. *Tehran Univ Med J* . 2021;79(7):563–7.
- XXIX. Şenel E, Ada S, Güleç AT, Çağlar B. Nicolau syndrome aggravated by cold application after i.m. diclofenac. *Journal of Dermatology*. 2008;35(1):18–20.
- XXX. Villarejo FJ, Pascual AM. Injection injury of the sciatic nerve (370 cases). *Child's nervous system*. 1993;9(4):229–32.
- XXXI. Şencan S, Cüce İ, Gündüz OH. Use of fluoroscopic-guided transsacral block for the treatment of iatrogenic post-injection sciatic neuropathy: Report of three cases. *Turk J Phys Med Rehabil*. 2019;65(4):406–10.
- XXXII. Villanueva P, Pittet LF, Curtis N. Management of Bacille Calmette-Guérin lymphadenitis and abscess in immunocompetent children: a

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- systematic review. *The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*. 2021;40(11):1037–45.
- XXXIII. Jahan T, Nehvi N, Farooq S. Post-vaccination Tubercular Cold Abscess of Thigh of An Infant. *JMID*. 2020;10(04):234–6.
- XXXIV. Mishra D, Mohta A, Arora P. Cold abscess of the thigh in an infant. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal*. 2013;11(1):86–7.
- XXXV. Sedighi P, Sadrosadat ST, Movahedi M, Sedighi I. BCG-Induced cold abscess as a complication of inadvertent vaccine injection: A case series. *Clinical Case Reports*. 2022;10(4):1–5.
- XXXVI. Nischal K, Basavaraj H, Swaroop M, Agrawal D, Sathyanarayana B, Umashankar N. Nicolau syndrome: An iatrogenic cutaneous necrosis. *J Cutan Aesthet Surg*. 2009;2(2):92–5.
- XXXVII. Ocak S, Ekici B, Çam H, Taştan Y. Nicolau syndrome after intramuscular benzathine penicillin treatment. *Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*. 2006;25(8):749.
- XXXVIII. Maitland K, Kiguli S, Opoka R, Engoru C, Olupot-Olupot P, Akech S, et al. Mortality after fluid bolus in African children with severe infection. *N Engl J Med*. 2011;364:2483–95.
- XXXIX. Edelson JB, Orenstein EW, Zaoutis LB, Copelovitch L. Intravenous Fluid Management in the Pediatric Hospital Setting: Is Isotonic Fluid the Right Approach for all Patients? *Current Treatment Options in Pediatrics*. 2015;1(1):90–9.
- XL. Lopes CLS, Piva JP. Fluid overload in children undergoing mechanical ventilation. *Rev Bras Ter Intensiva*. 2017;29(3):346–53.
- XLI. Bhandari DB, Mahalle AR, Premendran BJ, Dhande PS. Malfunctioning Pediatric infusion set leading to accidental fluid overload and pulmonary edema. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2014;30(4):579–81.
- XLII. Claire-Del Granado R, Mehta RL. Fluid overload in the ICU: Evaluation and management. *BMC Nephrol*. 2016;17:1–9.
- XLIII. Hayes W, Paglialonga F. Assessment and management of fluid overload in children on dialysis. *Pediatr Nephrol*. 2019;34(2):233–42.
- XLIV. Raina R, Sethi SK, Wadhvani N, Vemuganti M, Krishnappa V, Bansal SB. Fluid overload in critically ill children. *Front Pediatr*. 2018;6:1–18.
- XLV. Allinovi M, Saleem M, Romagnani P, Nazerian P, Hayes W. Lung ultrasound: A novel technique for detecting fluid overload in children on dialysis. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2017;32(3).
- XLVI. Anderson M, Dawson E. Accidents and poisoning. In: Lissauer T, Carroll W, Dinwiddie R, Hall M, editors. *The Science of Paediatrics MRCPCH Mastercourse*. Edinburgh: Elsevier; 2017. p. 101–17.
- XLVII. Proudfoot AT, Krenzelok EP, Vale JA. Position Paper on Urine Alkalinization. *Journal of Toxicology: Clinical Toxicology*. 2004;42(1):1–26.
- XLVIII. Ghannoum M, Roberts DM, Bouchard Josee. Enhanced Elimination of Poisons . In: Yu ASL, Chertow GM, Luyckx VA, Marsden PA, Skorecki K, Taal M, editors. *Brenner & Rector's The Kidney*. 4th ed. Elsevier; 2020. p. 2148–73.
- XLIX. Gummin DD, Mowry JB, Beuhler MC, Spyker DA, Bronstein AC, Rivers LJ, et al. 2020 Annual Report of the American Association of Poison Control Centers' National Poison Data System (NPDS): 38th Annual Report [Internet]. Vol. 59, *Clinical toxicology (Philadelphia, Pa.)*. 2021 [cited 2022 Aug 7]. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15563650.2021.1989785>
- L. Ouellet G, Bouchard J, Ghannoum M, Decker BS. Available extracorporeal treatments for poisoning: Overview and limitations. *Seminars in Dialysis*. 2014;27(4):342–9.
- LI. Dişel NR, Akpınar AA, Sebe A, Karakoç E, Sürer S, Turhan FT, et al. Therapeutic plasma exchange in poisoning: 8 years' experience of a university hospital. *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*. 2015;33(10):1391–5.